

Angelo Leogrande¹

GDP Growth Rate in Europe

Between 2010 and 2021 it grew by 2.2%

Eurostat calculates the value of the GDP growth rate for European countries. The GDP growth rate shows, in a relative sense from one year to the next, the trend in a country's capacity to produce added value.

Ranking of countries by change in Gross Domestic Product in 2021. Ireland ranks first by value of GDP growth rate in 2021 with an amount equal to 13.6%, followed by Croatia with an amount equal to 13.00% and from Montenegro equal to an amount of 13%. In the middle of the table are Cyprus with an amount equal to 6.6%, followed by Belgium with a value equal to 6.1% and Lithuania with an amount equal to 6%. The ranking is closed by Slovakia with an amount equal to 3%, Finland with a value equal to 3% and Germany with a value equal to 2.6%. On average, the GDP growth rate in 2021 was equal to an amount of 6.62%.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage change in the GDP growth rate between 2010 and 2021. Spain is in first place by the value of the percentage change in the GDP growth rate between 2010 and 2021 with a value of 2650 .00% equal to 5.30 units, followed by Serbia with a value equal to 971.43% equal to 6.80 units and by Ireland with a value equal to 700.00% equal to an amount of 11.90 units. In the middle of the table are Romania with an amount equal to 230.77% equal to 9.00 units, followed by Portugal with a value equal to 223.53% equal to 3.80 units and by Latvia with a value equal to 191 ,11% equal to 8.60 units. Sweden closes the ranking with a value equal to -15.00% equal to -0.90 units, followed by Germany with a value equal to -38.10% equal to -1.60 units and Slovakia with a value equal to -55.22% equal to -3.70 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is proposed below. The analysis shows the presence of two clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: Lithuania, Estonia, Latvia, Poland, Turkey, Romania, Ireland, Kosovo, Malta, Iceland, Hungary;
- Cluster 2: Norway, Luxembourg, Serbia, Switzerland, Denmark, Bosnia, Slovakia, Sweden, Bulgaria, Germany, Czech Republic, North Macedonia, Greece, Slovenia, Finland, Cyprus, Netherlands, Austria, Belgium, France, Croatia, Montenegro, Spain, Italy, Portugal.

From the point of view of the median, it appears that the value of Cluster 1-C1 with 7.1 exceeds the value of Cluster 2-C2 with 5.5 units. From a strictly geographical point of view, it appears that the Baltic countries and some Eastern European countries together with Turkey have a higher growth rate than other European countries.

Network Analysis with Manhattan Distance. The application of the network analysis with the Manhattan distance highlights the presence of a complex network structure and three simplified network structures. There is a complex network structure made up of Slovakia, Sweden, Germany, Switzerland, Denmark, Bosnia, the Netherlands, France, Austria, Belgium. Particularly:

- France has a connection with Belgium equal to an amount of 0.57 units, with Austria for a value equal to 0.64 units, with the Netherlands for a value equal to 1.1 units;

¹ Ph.D., Professor of Economics at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Statale 100 km 18, Bari, Puglia, Italy. Email: leogrande.cultura@lum.it

- Austria has a connection with France worth 0.64 units, with the Netherlands worth 0.67 units, with Belgium worth 0.83 units, and with the Germany with a value of 1.2 units;
- The Netherlands has a connection with France worth 1.1 units, with Austria worth 0.57 units, with Bosnia worth 1.1 units, with Denmark for a value equal to 0.82 units, with Belgium for a value equal to 0.96 units;
- Bosnia has a connection with the Netherlands worth 1.1 units, with Denmark worth 1.1 units;
- Denmark has a connection with Bosnia worth 1.1 units, with the Netherlands worth 0.82 units, with Germany worth 1.1 units and with Switzerland a value of 1.0 units;
- Belgium has a connection with France for a value of 0.85 units, with Austria for a value of 0.83 units, with the Netherlands equal to a value of 0.96 units, with Switzerland equal to a value of 1.1 units, with Germany equal to a value of 1.1 units;
- Switzerland has a connection with Belgium equal to a value of 1.1 units, with Denmark for a value equal to 1.0 units, with Germany for a value equal to 1.1 units;
- Germany has a connection with Austria with a value of 1.2 units, with Belgium with a value of 1.1 units, with Denmark with a value of 1.1 units with Switzerland with a value of 1.1 , units and with Sweden equal to a value of 1.0 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Germany for a value equal to 1.0 units and with Slovakia for a value equal to 1.1 units;
- Slovakia has a connection with Sweden worth 1.1 units.

In addition, there are three simplified network structures as follows:

- Lithuania and Estonia have a connection worth 1.0 units;
- Portugal and Spain have a connection worth 1.1 units;
- Slovenia and the Czech Republic have a connection value of 1.1 units.

The analysis shows that the most connected countries are Belgium and Germany. It follows that if Belgium and Germany have GDP growth then it is possible to activate a broad spillover effect that acts on most European countries, especially medium and high-income countries.

Conclusions. Calculating the average of the GDP growth rate between 2010 and 2021 for the European countries analyzed, there is a substantially increasing trend up to 2019. Between 2019 and 2020 the GDP growth rate decreased by an amount equal to 4, 3% to then grow between 2020 and 2021 by an amount equal to 6.6%. However, it is probable that the Russian-Ukrainian crisis and the restrictive monetary policies of the European central bank could reduce the GDP growth rate of European countries. Certainly, the European economy is not very reactive, especially from a financial and technological point of view. In fact, European banks and European financial markets appear to be undercapitalized compared to US banks and US financial markets. Europe is very backward in the knowledge economy and in the development of new technologies both in comparison with the USA and in comparison, with China and also with some Middle Eastern countries. Europe also has a further problem: the excess of SMEs lacking internationalization. It is therefore necessary that EU economic policy intervenes to remove these three enormous limits to GDP growth by creating the conditions for strengthening the European financial market, investing in new technologies, and offering incentives for mergers and acquisitions of SMEs.

Declarations

Acknowledgment. I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l., prof. Alberto Costantiello and prof. Lucio Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

References

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Exports of Goods and Services in European Countries in the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Estimation and Machine Learning Prediction of Imports of Goods in European Countries in the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, e-ISSN.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Exports of Knowledge Intensive Services. A Complex Metric Approach (No. 113348). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Export of Medium and High-Tech Products in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2022). The Export of High Knowledge Intensity Services of European Countries (No. 112795). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. University Library of Munich, Germany.

Appendix

Ranking dei paesi per tasso di crescita del PIL. Fonte: Eurostat					
Rank	GEO	2021	Rank	GEO	2021
1	<i>Ireland</i>	13,6	17	<i>Lithuania</i>	6
2	<i>Croatia</i>	13,1	18	<i>Spain</i>	5,5
3	<i>Montenegro</i>	13	18	<i>Portugal</i>	5,5
4	<i>Türkiye</i>	11,4	19	<i>Luxembourg</i>	5,1
5	<i>Kosovo</i>	10,7	19	<i>Romania</i>	5,1
6	<i>Malta</i>	10,3	19	<i>Sweden</i>	5,1
7	<i>Greece</i>	8,4	20	<i>Denmark</i>	4,9
8	<i>Slovenia</i>	8,2	20	<i>Netherlands</i>	4,9
9	<i>Estonia</i>	8	21	<i>Austria</i>	4,6
10	<i>Bulgaria</i>	7,6	22	<i>Iceland</i>	4,4
11	<i>Serbia</i>	7,5	23	<i>Switzerland</i>	4,2
12	<i>Hungary</i>	7,1	24	<i>Latvia</i>	4,1
12	<i>Bosnia and Herzego</i>	7,1	25	<i>North Macedon</i>	4
13	<i>France</i>	6,8	26	<i>Norway</i>	3,9
13	<i>Poland</i>	6,8	27	<i>Czechia</i>	3,5
14	<i>Italy</i>	6,7	28	<i>Slovakia</i>	3
15	<i>Cyprus</i>	6,6	28	<i>Finland</i>	3
16	<i>Belgium</i>	6,1	29	<i>Germany</i>	2,6

C1>C2

